

OCCUPATIONAL HYGIENE IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Annotation: In the modern distribution and use of the labor force, the factors of working conditions, the expectations of workers regarding the safety of the workplace, the quality of working life, and the preservation of health play an important role. In the organization of the workspace, social factors, factors of health-saving technologies are becoming increasingly important. International organizations are increasingly recording an increase in injuries, a deterioration in the quality of life of workers, including in such strata as the youth, which are important for the development of the labor market and society, which may pose a threat to reduce the human potential of the nation. The article provides international assessments of the understanding and calculation of the main indicators of working conditions, the quality of jobs and the health of workers, identifies the problems of further study in this area, reveals the features of the definition of the term "social occupational health" as significant for describing and clarifying the characteristics of modern labor relations, changes in relations between the employee and the employer in order to improve working conditions and employment, as well as social protection of the able-bodied population, maintaining and strengthening the health of employees.

Keywords: working conditions, decent work, social occupational health, quality of life, method.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational hygiene is a branch of hygiene that studies the conditions and nature of work, as well as their impact on the worker's ability to work and his health.

In this regard, the concept of the workplace, workplace ergonomics can be described as key criteria for occupational health, and the term "workplace ergonomics" itself can be defined identically to the concept of "occupational hygiene", including material, territorial, functional features as defining characteristics of the workplace.

Occupational health as a scientific direction also involves the development of approaches and methods aimed at preventing the harmful and dangerous effects of production factors on the labor activity of a person and on him as a person.

Modern working conditions, the development of production technologies are largely designed to increase the level of production, mechanize labor, facilitate the professional activities of the workforce, but at the same time, the main indicators of injuries at work, the proportion of

occupational diseases, deterioration of physical and psychological The health of workers remains sufficient for the need to study this problem and find solutions to optimize working conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The very concept of social hygiene at the state level in order to regulate the conditions of interaction in society was defined as significant in the second half of the 20th century. and was determined as the science of the laws of public health.

In this regard, the concept of "social occupational health" should be defined as a scientific direction about the patterns of formation and change of health in work collectives, defined as a system of interrelated aspects of individual health, taking into account the synergistic effect of collective interactions.

The term "social hygiene" itself was introduced into scientific circulation in the first half of the 19th century. J. A. Rochou. In the middle of the 19th century, when defining the concept of chronic occupational diseases, the term "social hygiene" was used in the work of E. Furko.

The study of the influence of social factors on the health of a person and the population as a whole was devoted to the works of A. Grotyan, A. Fisher, N. A. Semashko [5], Z. P. Solovyov.

In particular, N. A. Semashko defined as the main task of social hygiene a deep study of the influence of the social environment on human health, aspects of his research were the development of measures to eliminate the harmful effects of the social environment on health and working capacity.

Another definition of the concept of "social hygiene" is its understanding as a science of public health, of social problems that affect the health of the population. Thus, the definition of health in a social context is considered in the work of Z. G. Frenkel, the study of the influence of socio-economic and social relations on the health of the population is defined in the work of A. F. Serenko. Opportunities to improve health in teams through social factors are considered in the works of E. Y. Belitskaya [5]. Especially the issues of consideration of social health were relevant for socialist societies and were considered, in particular, in the works of P. V. Kolarov [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Occupational health is defined as one of the main functions of the World Health Organization (WHO), which is normatively enshrined in the charter of the organization, according to which WHO efforts should be directed, among other things, to improving working conditions and social hygiene.

The studies note the connection between the development of society and social hygiene, therefore the very phenomenon of social hygiene is important for study within the framework of WHO, while the definition of social hygiene is carried out multi-criteria, such as the risks of occupational diseases, injuries at work, the impact of industrial and social factors, accessibility of health services.

All approaches to the need to control the health of workers are defined within the framework of the global action plan for the protection of workers' health and find practical application from 2008 to 2022.

The International Labor Organization (ILO) is also considering the preservation and promotion of the health of the workforce. The ILO defines the concept of "occupational disease" as developing as a result of exposure to risk factors in the course of work.

Associated with the concept of an occupational disease is the concept of occupational risk, as the probability of a health disorder, while the degree of risk is determined by the severity of the health disorder.

The main methods of such studies are historical, analytical, factorial, principal component method, comparative analysis method, econometric methods of evaluation.

Defining youth as a group aged 15–24 years, it is important to emphasize their significant number, on the one hand, in the total population of the world (about 540 million) and a significant proportion of young people in the working population (more than 15% of the population). most of the power of the world falls on this age group). At the same time, this age group is determined by both significant social risks and health risks.

Thus, the level of occupational injuries in the workplace in this group is 40% higher than in the age groups over 25 years old. It is especially important that 37 million of the youth stratum are workers aged 15-17 who are engaged in hazardous work. It is important to note the significant proportion among young people of those who work in the informal and shadow sectors with appropriate working conditions, as well as the fact that early labor socialization distorts the general value professional orientation of young people, reduces the quality of the labor force, and negatively affects the indicator of the level the human capital of the nation.

The 2018 World Day for Safety and Health at Work conference highlights the critical importance of addressing the safety and health of young workers, not only to promote decent employment for young people, but also to combine these efforts to combat hazardous and all other forms of youth group work .

CONCLUSION

According to the WHO, which has studied the factors that determine the health of the population of the developing countries of the world, the state of health of the population depends on the following reasons:

- socio-economic conditions and lifestyle by 48-53%;
- genetic factors (prevalence of hereditary diseases) by 18-20%;
- quality (degree of pollution) of the environment by 17-20%;
- the level of development and quality of medical care by 8–10% [2].

Determining the importance of socio-economic conditions and lifestyle in the formation of a general indicator of health, we will define another similar indicator - estimates of decent work.

According to the ILO, decent work reflects people's aspirations for their working lives. It includes opportunities for productive work that provides a fair income, workplace safety and social protection for families, better prospects for personal development and social inclusion, the freedom of people to express their concerns, organize and participate in decisions that affect their lives, and equality of opportunity and treatment for all women and men.

Since 2014, there has been an increase in the growth trend of the category of “working poor”. At the same time, there are no qualitative increments in the labor force; labor productivity has practically not changed over the period under review.

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